

The Influence of Martial arts on the Development of Modern Dance

¹Drach Tamara Leonidivna, ²Cymbalyuk Olena Kostyantynivna,

¹post-graduate student of Lviv State University of Physical Culture named after Ivan Bobersky,

Trainer –choreographer of dance-studio Chocolate, c. Lviv

²Candidate of Art History, Associate Professor of the Department of Choreography and Art History of Lviv State University of Physical Culture named after Ivan Bobersky

Summary: *Modern choreography has absorbed the experimental search for new dancing movements, due to the combination of spiritual practices and the latest trends in culture. In addition to the influence of yoga or free plastic on the development of modern dance, the martial arts, which also explores the inner feelings of human and his interaction with a partner and space, had a great influence on the modern-dance. Martial arts develop a person's self-discipline and self-confidence, it teaches self-defense, however, the vast majority of martial arts do not require aggression, but only use the energy of the enemy for our own self-preservation. The ways in which this is achieved are called martial arts techniques. In modern choreography, this is distinguished by performance techniques, among them, modern dance techniques, for example, are the choreographic techniques of Martha Graham, Merce Cunningham, Charles Weidman, Jose Limon. The technique of the last one is dominated by the dynamics of fall and reflection in the movements of human nature. Much attention is paid to gravity, inertia, weight, energy and momentum, which is typical of martial arts techniques. The technique is closely related to breathing, which also resonates with yoga and oriental practices. So, we decided to explore the impact of martial arts on the development of modern dance, including modern dance. Thanks to the research, we analyzed the literary sources and made an art analysis of the works of modern choreographers, thus determining the impact of martial arts on the development of modern dance.*

Keywords: *modern dance, mutual influence of traditions, martial arts, buto, aikido, capoeira, ballet performance.*

I. Formulation of the problem.

Nowadays we can see the heyday of modern choreography, it is used in their performances by choreographers for ballet productions, who are seeking to the reflection of the modern plastic realities and problems of society, they try to reflect changes in its aesthetics and principles. Each style of modern dance is distinguished by its dancing movements, which characterizes a particular choreographer. One of the current fashion trends is the use of martial arts in dance performances. It is used not only in dramatic productions, where the actors' play involves the use of stage plastics, but also according to the director's plan can be used techniques of modern martial arts. However, ballet performances do not deviate from such innovations, because very often choreographers who work with ballet dancers use the plastic movements of martial arts. This is the question we decided to explore in our research.

II. Analysis of recent publications:

Sources of modern choreography have been studied by such scientists as Plahotniuk O.A. (2016), Sharikov D.I. (2010), Nikitin V. Yu. (2000). However, the question of the influence of martial arts on the development of

modern choreography has not yet been reflected in modern literature. The question of today's modern dance and the interaction of these two areas is still poorly understood. After all, more than a century has passed since the emergence of the modern style and the revolution in dance, and the latest trends in the development of modern choreography include the influence of martial arts and oriental trends on the vocabulary of dance performances.

III. Selection of previously unsolved parts of the overall problem.

The question of today's modern dance and the interaction of other areas on the development of this type of choreography still has been studied a little. Only a century has passed since the emergence of the modern style and the "revolution" in dance, and the latest trends in the development of modern choreography have included the influence of other arts, martial arts, in particular, oriental trends on the vocabulary of dance performances.

IV. Formulation of the purpose of the article.

That is why we set a purpose: to investigate the influence of martial arts on the development of modern choreography. To achieve this purpose we should solve the following tasks: analyze the literature on this issue; to conduct an art analysis of the work of modern choreographers, in which we can see the influence of martial arts on the creation of choreographic vocabulary.

V. Presentation of the main research material.

Modern choreography is constantly evolving, new styles and trends are emerging. Modern dance techniques have different interpretations, so it is important to explore where modern choreography comes from and how new interesting means of expression emerge. Eastern culture had a great influence on the development of modern dance.

Deepening in our own feelings is characteristic of oriental martial arts. Where a person delves not only into the form and technique of execution, but also observes his own inner state. It is important to trace the development of this idea in the martial arts of the East and spiritual practices that have been transferred to modern choreography, and modern dance in particular. We notice in many martial arts appeals to the elements: wind, water, fire, earth. They inspired recognized sensei to create martial arts, you can see how in the martial art of aikido people perform movements resembling the figures and images of a tsunami, stones or trees, it is appropriate in modern dances, where a person can reproduce the movement of fire, water or air. These simple and clear things inspired Isadora Duncan to search for free art, she multiplied this wealth of cultural heritage of mankind, and created her own dance. Martial arts improve the culture of combat, give martial arts forms, which when practiced create a tool to counter aggression and attacks. Teachers went beyond the technique of execution and created the psychology of combat, tactics, education of wisdom and martial etiquette, which help people move away from aggression and redirect negative emotions and feelings into harmony and perfection. It was these techniques that were used by Ruth Saint-Denis, who sought inspiration for productions in Eastern culture. And Loï Fuller experimented with attributes, light, used unusual costumes, it significantly revived the development of modern dance and its techniques [1, p.45].

Martial arts techniques resonate best with contact improvisation, where the partner must feel the impulse of his opponent in order to make a new movement and use his energy. Contact improvisation is also present in martial arts, when *jo waza* (performing free techniques) is done. When a partner does not know how he will be attacked by *uke* and must react immediately.

Aikido, for example, is also called *Japanese dance* because it looks like people dance when performing techniques. However, these combat techniques do not become less effective. *Aikido* is a martial art that originated in Japan and was founded by Morihei Ueshiba. In aikido legs are covered with special long pants (*hakama*), which hide the movements of the legs, it seems that a person slides on the floor, which also creates

the illusion of theatricality. In addition, in Aikido there are no kicks, which creates a mundane movement in the process of techniques, reminiscent of the movements of modern dance [4, p.57].

Capoeira, also a form of Brazilian martial art, has a musical accompaniment of *berimbau*, a single-stringed musical instrument, or other national instruments, which also suggests that the partners seem to be dancing. The capoeira has many elements performed on the hands, so it seems that a person fills all the levels of space, the movement must be continuous. This is typical of the modern direction of *contemporary dance* art, where movements flow smoothly from each other. It seems that the performer obeys some element and falls into a "dancing trance", over time, practice helps to achieve continuity of movement, the body begins to move under the influence of internal energy. The style of modern Japanese *buto* choreography includes such elements as concentration, performance of static poses, as it is characteristic of *kung fu*. The performer freezes in one position on one or two legs and looks for inner balance. *Buto* is a modern type of dance, where the movement takes place in the middle of the performer, not outside [2, p.8].

Another martial art that has influenced the development of choreography, modern in particular, is *martial hopak* - the Ukrainian national martial art, which already in its name reflects the essence of dance. The fighter seems to dance, performing combat techniques, but this format helps to cultivate endurance and maneuverability in warriors, when the performer feels the rhythm and tact, reacts faster to attacks and makes the necessary hook and blow in time. Thus, power in movements and grace in performing techniques are achieved, which become an effective means to combat the enemy and their own weaknesses [3, p.50]. *Martial hopak* is a popular martial art in Ukraine. In productions of choreographer Iryna Mazur draws on modern choreography and stylizes it in the national folk style. It combines elements of martial arts of Ukraine, national cultural heritage, Ukrainian folk choreography and creates a costumed action, which gives rise to the creation of original national productions. Fighting hopak, present in her choreographic production "*Revolution*", which reflects the struggle of the Ukrainian people for independence and freedom.

Turning to the martial arts of Ukraine, it should be noted the martial art of the Ukrainian Amazons *Asgarda*, who also used dance as a way to achieve martial excellence. And now this art is transmitted and reflected in the search for Ukrainian modern choreographers [3, p.55].

It is important to note that the martial arts of East and West differ in their approach to the inner state of the warrior and his professional characteristics. Therefore, it is important that the eastern martial arts brought to the choreography a deepening of the inner state of the performer, and the western ones gave shape, created a vessel in which the choreographers of modern dance later forms their performances.

VI. Conclusions from this research and prospects.

Thus, we can conclude that martial arts have a significant impact on the development of modern choreography. The analysis of literary sources allowed us to trace the influence of Eastern martial arts on the development of modern dance, and art analysis of Ukrainian choreographers helped to find common features in the vocabulary of modern choreography and national martial arts. Prospects for future research - is to study the development of amateur modern dance. It is among amateurs that the study of dance techniques - modernism, its latest trends and innovations - is currently becoming popular. The influence of martial arts on the development of modern choreography is only one side of the coin, because now we can see a significant contribution of yoga, oriental practices and culture to the emergence of new principles of modern choreography. Modern dance absorbs new ideas that are realized on the stage by choreographers in Ukraine, *Alla Rubina*, *Lyudmila Popovych*, *Tetyana Ostroverkh*, *Rada Poklitaru*, *Iryna Mazur* and others. They are seeking ways to bring the art of modern dance to the Ukrainian audience, looking for new interesting lexical and emotional means to promote modern dance culture.

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